

DYNAMIC RESPONSES OF ORTHOTROPIC ANNULAR COMPOSITE PLATES

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SUMMARY: Using Hamilton's principle, the nonlinear partial differential for large oscillations and the associated boundary conditions, for thick circular composite plates, have been derived. A high-order shear deformation thick plate theory rather than a first-order shear deformation plate theory is implemented in the basic equations. The applications of the finite element method to the dynamic problems rely on the use of a variational principle to derive the necessary element properties and motion equations. The assembled equations for an eigenvalue problem. A numerical technique of using an incremental and iterative scheme is utilized for calculating frequency responses. The HSG-PRD-HSG and PRD-HSG-PRD annular composite plate with free-clamped boundary conditions are studied as examples and their dynamic responses are obtained.

KEYWORDS: non-linear dynamic response, thick annular composite plates

INTRODUCTION

Composite plates are made of laminae, the plates can be layers of isotropic or anisotropic materials which material properties may or may not depend on orientation. The plates are heterogeneous in thicknesswise because of difference material layers. Also the thickness of plates may be thick enough for which the "thin" plate theory might not be sufficient to describe the physical models. Thus, the equations of motion of a heterogeneous anisotropic thick plate are needed. Using Hamilton's principle, the nonlinear partial differential equations for large oscillations and the associated boundary conditions have been derived. A higher-order shear deformation plate theory (the inplane displacements are expressed as a cubic polynomial functions of thickness coordinate and the transverse deflection is assumed to be a constant) rather than a first-order shear deformation plate theory is implemented in the basic equations. The applications of the finite element method to the dynamic problems rely on the use of a variational principle to derive the necessary element properties and equations. The assembled finite-element equations for the plate are formed by summing each element equation obtained in consideration of a single element. Then, the boundary conditions are imposed on the vector of nodal field variables, so that the appropriate boundary conditions are satisfied. The assembled equations form an eigenvalue problem. The developed model is then applied to study an axisymmetric large vibration of heterogeneous orthotropic annular composite plate. A numerical technique of using an incremental and iterative scheme is utilized for calculating frequency responses. The HSG-PRD-HSG (High-Strength-Graphite epoxy sandwiched with two filaments of PRD-49-III developed by E.I. DuPont de Nemours and Company, Inc.) and PRD-HSG-PRD annular composite plates with free-clamped boundary conditions, are used as examples, and their dynamic responses are obtained. The effects of thickness of plate which are due to the shear deformation, rotatory inertia, inplane deformation and inplane inertia, are examined and discussed.

EQUATIONS OF MOTION IN FINITE ELEMENT FORM

According to the higher order shear deformation plate theory (Reddy, 1984) [1], the displacements of an axisymmetric polar orthotropic annular plate can be expressed as:

$$u_r = u_r^0 + z \left[\Psi_r - \frac{4}{3} \left(\frac{z}{h} \right)^2 (\Psi_r + w_{,r}) \right], \quad (1a)$$

$$u_z = w(r, t), \quad (1b)$$

where u_r and u_z are respectively the inplane displacements in the radial and transverse directions, u_r^0 and w are the midplane displacements in the radial and transverse directions, respectively, $w_{,r}$ (partial derivative of w with respect to r) is the slope of the midplane, and Ψ_r is the rotation of the normal to the midplane.

Following the Von Karman theory of flat plates, the strain-displacement relations are:

$$\varepsilon_{rr} = \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial r} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial r} \right)^2, \quad \varepsilon_{\theta\theta} = \frac{u_r}{r}, \quad \gamma_{rz} = \frac{\partial w}{\partial r} + \frac{\partial u_r}{\partial z}. \quad (2)$$

For polar orthotropic material, the stress-strain relations are:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_{rr} \\ \sigma_{\theta\theta} \\ \sigma_{rz} \end{Bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{11} & Q_{12} & 0 \\ Q_{12} & Q_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{55} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_{rr} \\ \varepsilon_{\theta\theta} \\ \gamma_{rz} \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (3)$$

where the reduced plane-stress elastic constants, Q_{ij} , are in terms of the moduli and Poisson's ratios,

$$Q_{11} = \frac{E_r}{1 - \nu_{r\theta}\nu_{\theta r}}, \quad Q_{12} = \frac{\nu_{r\theta}E_r}{1 - \nu_{r\theta}\nu_{\theta r}}, \quad (4)$$

$$Q_{22} = \frac{E_\theta}{1 - \nu_{r\theta}\nu_{\theta r}}, \quad Q_{55} = E_{rz}.$$

The following nondimensional parameters are introduced:

$$\chi = w/r_0, \quad \Psi_\xi = \Psi_r, \quad u_\xi^0 = u_r^0/h, \quad u_\xi = u_r/h, \quad (5)$$

$$\xi = r/r_0, \quad R = r_i/r_0, \quad \zeta = z/h.$$

The energy approach is used in this paper for solving the problem considered. Since the plate is axisymmetric, ring elements are chosen. The normalized region of the plate $[R, 1]$ is

divided into n finite elements, each having a width $2s$, where $s = (1 - R)/2n$. Each element has three nodes (two exterior nodes and one interior node) and each nodal point has four degrees of freedom, u_ξ^0 , Ψ_ξ , χ_ξ , and $\chi_{,\xi}$.

The kinetic and strain energy of an annular plate subjected to axisymmetric vibrations can be expressed as:

$$T = \frac{1}{2} \rho \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} \int_1^R \left[\left(h \frac{\partial u_\xi}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(r_0 \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right] h r^2 d\xi d\zeta d\theta, \quad (6a)$$

$$V = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^{2\pi} \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} \int_1^R \{ \varepsilon \}^T [Q] \{ \varepsilon \} h r^2 d\xi d\zeta d\theta. \quad (6b)$$

The nondimensional inplane displacements for a finite element are expressed as:

$$u^0_{\xi}(\xi, t) = \sum_{i=1}^3 N_i(\xi) U_i(t), \quad (7a)$$

$$\Psi_{\xi}(\xi, t) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \phi_i(\xi) W_i(t), \quad (7b)$$

$$\chi(\xi, t) = \sum_{i=1}^3 \phi_i(\xi) W_i(t), \quad (7c)$$

where U_i , V_i and W_i are nodal variable vectors, defined as:

$$\{U_i\} = [U_1 \ U_2 \ U_3]^T, \quad (8a)$$

$$\{V_i\} = [V_1 \ V_2 \ V_3]^T, \quad (8b)$$

$$\{W_i\} = [W_1 \ W_{1,\xi} \ W_2 \ W_{2,\xi} \ W_3 \ W_{3,\xi}]^T, \quad (8c)$$

and the shape functions ρ_i and N_i are (Huang and Huang, 1989):

$$\{\phi_i\} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.75 & -0.5 & -1.25 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.25 & -0.25 & -0.25 & 0.25 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 & -2 & 0 & 1 \\ 1 & 0 & -2 & 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -0.75 & -0.5 & 1.25 & 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0.25 & 0.25 & -0.25 & -0.25 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \eta^5 \\ \eta^4 \\ \eta^3 \\ \eta^2 \\ \eta \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (9a)$$

$$\{N_i\} = \begin{bmatrix} 0.5 & -0.5 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & 1 \\ 0.5 & 0.5 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} \eta^2 \\ \eta \\ 1 \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (9b)$$

The strain vector $\{\epsilon\}$ in eqn (6b) can be separated into a linear part and a nonlinear part as:

$$\{\epsilon\} = \{\epsilon^L\} + \{\epsilon^{NL}\} = \begin{Bmatrix} \{\epsilon^L_p\} \\ \{\epsilon^L_b\} \\ \{\epsilon^L_s\} \end{Bmatrix} + \begin{Bmatrix} \{\epsilon^{NL}_p\} \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (10)$$

where supercripts L and NL denote linear and nonlinear, respectively, and subscripts of p , b and s represent inplane, bending and shear strains, respectively. The linear strain components are:

$$\{\varepsilon^L_p\} = \frac{h}{r_0} \begin{Bmatrix} \partial u^0_\xi / \partial \xi \\ u^0_\xi / \xi \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (11a)$$

$$\{\varepsilon^L_b\} = \frac{z}{r_0} \begin{Bmatrix} \Psi_{\xi,\xi} \\ \Psi_{\xi\xi} \end{Bmatrix} - \frac{4}{3h^2} \frac{z^3}{r_0} \begin{Bmatrix} \Psi_{\xi,\xi} + \chi_{,\xi\xi} \\ (1/\xi) (\Psi_\xi + \chi_{,\xi}) \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (11b)$$

$$\{\varepsilon^L_s\} = (1 - 4\zeta^2) (\Psi_\xi + \chi_{,\xi}), \quad (11c)$$

and the nonlinear inplane component is expressed as:

$$\varepsilon^{NL}_p = \frac{1}{2} (\chi_{,\xi})^2 = f(\chi_{,\xi}), \quad (11d)$$

where f , the linearized function, is defined as:

$$f = \frac{1}{2} \chi_{,\xi}. \quad (12)$$

Substituting eqn (7) into (11), strain components are expressed in terms of shape functions:

$$\{\varepsilon^L_p\} = \frac{h}{r_0} \begin{bmatrix} \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial \xi} & 0 & 0 \\ N_i & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_i \\ V_i \\ W_i \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (13a)$$

$$\{\varepsilon^L_b\} = \frac{z}{r_0} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial \xi} & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{N_i}{\xi} & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_i \\ V_i \\ W_i \end{Bmatrix} - \frac{4}{3h^2} \frac{z^3}{r_0} \begin{bmatrix} 0 & \frac{\partial N_i}{\partial \xi} & \frac{\partial^2 \phi_i}{\partial \xi^2} \\ 0 & \frac{N_i}{\xi} & \frac{1}{\xi} \frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial \xi} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_i \\ V_i \\ W_i \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (13b)$$

$$\{\varepsilon^L_s\} = (1 - 4\zeta^2) \begin{bmatrix} 0 & N_i & \frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial \xi} \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_i \\ V_i \\ W_i \end{Bmatrix}, \quad (13c)$$

$$\{\varepsilon^{NL}_p\} = f \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & \frac{\partial \phi_i}{\partial \xi} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{Bmatrix} U_i \\ V_i \\ W_i \end{Bmatrix}. \quad (13d)$$

The kinetic and strain energies of a ring element of the plate subjected to harmonic

oscillations are:

$$T^{(e)} = \frac{1}{2} 2\pi\rho \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} \int_{\xi_i}^{\xi_{i+1}} \left[\left(h \frac{\partial u \xi}{\partial t} \right)^2 + \left(r_0 \frac{\partial \chi}{\partial t} \right)^2 \right] h r^2 \xi d\xi d\zeta, \quad (14a)$$

$$V^{(e)} = \frac{1}{2} 2\pi \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} \int_{\xi_i}^{\xi_{i+1}} \{\varepsilon\}^T [Q] \{\varepsilon\} h r^2 \xi d\xi d\zeta. \quad (14b)$$

The strain energy is separated into two parts, namely the linear strain energy $V_L^{(e)}$ and the nonlinear strain energy $V_{NL}^{(e)}$. They are as follows:

$$V_L^{(e)} = \pi \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} \int_{\xi_i}^{\xi_{i+1}} \{\varepsilon^L\}^T [Q] \{\varepsilon^L\} h r^2 \xi d\xi d\zeta, \quad (15a)$$

$$V_{NL}^{(e)} = \pi \int_{-1/2}^{1/2} \int_{\xi_i}^{\xi_{i+1}} \left[\{\varepsilon^{NL}\}^T [Q]^k \{\varepsilon^L\} + \{\varepsilon^L\}^T [Q]^k \{\varepsilon^{NL}\} \right. \\ \left. + \{\varepsilon_{NL}\}^T [Q]^k \{\varepsilon_{NL}\} \right] h r^2 \xi d\xi d\zeta. \quad (15b)$$

Applying Hamilton's principle and carrying out the first variation of the energy functional:

$$\delta \int_{t_1}^{t_2} (T^{(e)} + V^{(e)}) dt = 0, \quad (16)$$

one obtains the basic equation of motion in the finite element from:

$$([K]^{(e)} - \omega^2 [M]^{(e)}) \{\Delta\}^{(e)} = 0, \quad (17)$$

where the element stiffness matrix $[K]^{(e)}$ and element mass matrix $[M]^{(e)}$ are:

$$[K]^{(e)} = [K]^{(e)}_L + [K]^{(e)}_{NL} \\ = \begin{bmatrix} [K^{11}]_L & [K^{12}]_L & [K^{13}]_L \\ [K^{12}]^T_L & [K^{22}]_L & [K^{23}]_L \\ [K^{13}]^T_L & [K^{23}]^T_L & [K^{33}]_L \end{bmatrix}^{(e)} + \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & [K^{13}]_{NL} \\ 0 & 0 & 0 \\ [K^{13}]^T_{NL} & 0 & [K^{33}]_{NL} \end{bmatrix}^{(e)}, \quad (18)$$

$$[M]^{(e)} = \begin{bmatrix} [M^{11}] & [M^{12}] & [M^{13}] \\ [M^{12}]^T & [M^{22}] & [M^{23}] \\ [M^{13}]^T & [M^{23}]^T & [M^{33}] \end{bmatrix}^{(e)}. \quad (19)$$

The details of stiffness coefficients $[K^{\hat{ij}}]$ and mass coefficients $[M^{\hat{ij}}]$ are listed in the Ref [2].

The global form of the equation of motion is:

$$([K] - \omega^2 [M]) \{\Delta\} = 0, \quad (20)$$

where $[K]$ and $[M]$ represent global stiffness matrix and mass matrix, respectively. The boundary conditions for Free-Clamp Case are:

$$\{U\} = [U_1, U_2, \dots, U_n, 0]^T, \quad (21a)$$

$$\{V\} = [V_1, V_2, \dots, V_n, 0]^T, \tag{21b}$$

$$\{W\} = [W_1, W_{1,\xi}, W_2, W_{2,\xi}, \dots, W_n, W_{n,\xi}, 0, 0]^T. \tag{21c}$$

With the boundary conditions, for linear vibrations, eqn (20) can be solved directly by numerical computation to obtain the frequencies ω by using a standard algorithm. For nonlinear vibrations, the nonlinear part of element stiffness matrix $[K]^{(e)}_{NL}$ contains the unknown function f in eqn (17), and an iterative procedure (Raju and Rao, 1982) [3] must be used to find their frequency responses. A computer code is written for the purpose of obtaining numerical results.

NUMERICAL RESULT AND DISCUSSION

In the numerical calculations, the total thickness of the plate h is chosen as 6.35 mm, and the ratio of outer radius-thickness (r_0/h) is taken as 10 and 25, as the thick and thin annular sandwich plates, (see Figure 1) respectively. Two interior hole sizes are used, i.e. $R = r_0/r_0 = 0.1$ and 0.3. The material properties of HSG and PRD-49 III are listed below:

Material	density ρ $\text{kg/m}^3 \times 10^3$	E_{11} $\text{N/m}^2 \times 10^{10}$	E_{22} $\text{N/m}^2 \times 10^{10}$	E_{55} $\text{N/m}^2 \times 10^{10}$	ν_{12}	ν_{21}
High-strength graphite epoxy (HSG)	1.558	12.40	1.03	0.55	0.27	0.0224
PRD-490 III epoxy (PRD)	1.391	7.93	0.41	0.21	0.30	0.0155

With these material properties, the element matrices in equations (18) and (19) and the basic equation (20), the frequency responses are obtained and plotted in Figures.

Figures 2 and 3 show the linear frequency, affected by the variation of sandwiched thickness ratio of annular sandwich plates, comprised of PRD 49-III and HSG with $r_0/h=25$ (thin plate) and 10 (thick plate), respectively. Both show that, for a given sandwiched thickness ratio value of $2h_f/h$, the linear frequency response of a HSG-PRD-HSG annular sandwich plate is higher than that of a PRD-HSG-PRD annular sandwich plate. The homogeneous HSG annular plate ($2h_{f(\text{PRD})}/h=0$ or $2h_{f(\text{HSG})}/h=1$) has a higher frequency response than the homogeneous PRD annular plate ($2h_{f(\text{HSG})}/h=0$ or $2h_{f(\text{PRD})}/h=1$). The frequency response of a annular sandwich plate comprised of PRD core with HSG facings is higher than that of a homogeneous PRD plate. On the contrary, the frequency response of an annular sandwich plate with HSG core and PRD facing is lower than that of a homogeneous HSG plate. Figure 2 shows the frequency of HSG-PRD-HSG annular sandwich plates increases with an increase of the sandwiched thickness ratio. The maximum frequency occurs approximately at $2h_f/h=0.8$ for both hole sizes $R=0.1$ and 0.3. The frequency decreases slightly when the ratio $2h_f/h$ is greater than 0.8. The frequency at $2h_f/h=0$ is the frequency of a homogeneous HSG plate. In Figure 3, the frequency of HSG-PRD-HSG annular sandwich plate increases monotonically with an increase of the sandwiched thickness ratio, and reaches the maximum

value, which is the frequency of the homogeneous plate made of HSG. In comparison of Figures 2 and 3, the characteristics of frequency curves with respect to sandwiched thickness ratio are similar with some variations. This phenomena is due to the effects of shear deformation and rotatory inertia which must be included in the thick plate theory.

Figure 4 shows the frequency ratio ω_{NL}/ω_L versus the sandwiched thickness ratio $2h_f/h$ at the finite amplitude of $w_{max}/h=1.0$. The PRD-HSG-PRD annular sandwich plate has higher frequency ratio than that of HSG-PRD-HSG annular sandwich plate for $0 < 2h_f/h < 0.7$. The maximum frequency ratio ω_{NL}/ω_L occurs approximately at $2h_f/h=0.4$ for the annular sandwich plate comprised of HSG core with PRD facings. At the highest frequency ratio, the frequencies of nonlinear vibrations are 5.2% and 1.81% higher than those of linear vibrations, respectively.

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Figure 1

Figure 2: Linear Frequency Responses for Various Thickness Ratios of Thin Plates

Figure 3. Linear Frequency Response for Various Sandwiched Thickness Ratio of Thick Plates

Figure 4. Nonlinear Frequency Response for Various Thickness Ratio of Thin Plates